

COMMENTARY SPEECH AND COMMENTING SKILLS IN SPORTS GAMES

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Abstract. Professional sports are gambling, dynamic, unpredictable, causing strong emotions, as a rule, they are shown live on television. An important role in television sports journalism is played by sports commentary. The article discusses these criteria.

Keywords: commentator's speech, method, sports commentary, spontaneous speech, tropes.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, a large number of people show interest in the field of sports, in this regard, sports reports on television and on the Internet attract a lot of attention from viewers. It is the commentator who helps many people who do not understand the rules to understand why the player was fined, because of which the player was removed from the court, what is the reason for watching a fragment of the game, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The analysis of the speech of sports commentators is of great interest in linguistics. The study of this genre began relatively recently. But in a short period of time, a large amount of research has been carried out in this area. In their works, the authors focus on such aspects as the use of tropes and language structures, spontaneous and prepared speech, communicative clarity, analysis of errors in the commentator's speech, etc. So, for example, in the article "Individual-author's metaphors in a television sports report" by T.P. Kuranova talks about the role of individual metaphors in sports commentary [8, p. 79]. It is thanks to the large number of metaphors that the commentator is able to evoke associations in the audience. E.K. Ziyangirov in the article "Linguistic structure of a sports football match" talks about the uniqueness of the genre, as it combines spontaneous speech and prepared constructions. This is related to the sport that the reporter is commenting on. The author refers to the classification of sports by D. Motson, according to which sports events are divided into fast (water polo), slow (race walking) and rhythmic (volleyball) [6, p. 462-463].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It should be noted that fast sports (football, hockey, basketball) are of greater interest to researchers than swimming, which belongs to both slow and fast sports. Swimming includes a large number of subspecies: sports swimming, synchronized swimming, water polo, etc. Each of these subspecies can be attributed to different sports in terms of dynamics.

The formation of sports commentary as a genre is associated with the technical development of the media. This genre has made its way from radio broadcasting to the Internet. The latter is very popular today.

From the terminological dictionary of V. Egorov, it follows that a commentary is "a speech by a specialist with an original text about an event, a fact with a certain assessment that

reveals the author's position" [4]. According to this definition, two main words "author's position" can be distinguished. This shows that the commentary is subjective.

There are many different classifications of the commentary genre, among them there are two types of commentary according to the way they are included in the program of the broadcast day:

1. Independent transfer (or a certain independent structural unit of a more complex program);
2. A brief comment, which is included as an integral element in the information and analytical news release.

The main purpose of the first type is to convey the essence of the event. The commentator should create the integrity of the picture so that the viewer or listener has a complete understanding of what is happening in the center of events. The second type carries the information load. It conveys the most necessary information for the viewer or listener [4, p. 61-62].

A sportscaster has to understand a large number of disciplines. He needs to know the rules of the sport he is commenting on, the names of active athletes and athletes of previous years in order to compare their results. Also, the commentator must be competent in sports events. As a rule, preparations for major competitions take place over a long period of time, as a result of which news may appear that will be related to athletes and not only. Many events that take place long before the start of the event have an impact on athletes and coaches, which can lead to a positive or negative outcome. The task of the commentator is to explain the causal relationships of events.

As you know, sports commentary consists of spontaneous speech with prepared elements. Depending on the sport, the commentator will use a certain amount of prepared information. Accordingly, from the term "prepared speech" it follows that the commentator prepares in advance exhaustive information about the sporting event that he will comment on. A prepared speech is needed in order to inform the viewer of interesting facts during pauses.

Sports commentary involves live communication with the viewer. This refers to spontaneous speech, due to the fact that the commentator is talking about what is happening at the moment. From an article by G.A. Tezekbayeva follows that

“Spontaneous speech is carried out by the speaker in constantly changing communicative conditions. That is why spontaneous speech is an indicator of the level of language competence of the speaker” [1, p. 76]. It follows that the knowledge of the Russian language by a commentator must be at a high level in order to clearly and correctly formulate their thoughts.

Spontaneous speech is characterized by such phenomena as hesitations (pauses) and repetitions. The use of these phenomena shows us that the commentator is formulating his thought. They can also emphasize the semantic and emotional aspect of speech, which makes statements more expressive.

Hesitation pauses are divided into unfilled, forming a break in the sound, and filled. Filled hesitation pauses include vocalizations (uh, mmm); puffs of sounds - lengthening of vowels or consonants (“we saw you yesterday in a cafe”); parasitic words or introductory empty words (“so to speak”, “well”, “here”); metatextual comments addressed to the addressee or to oneself, thanks to them contact with the interlocutor is ensured (“as you know”, “you understand”, etc.); unintentional repetitions (“I wanted-la”), full repetition of the word (“he won-

won the race”), non-verbal pauses of hesitation: coughs, sighs, laughter, clatter of the tongue; self-interruptions, restarts - repeated starts (“Champion ... World Junior Champion”), and false starts - unsuccessful starts (“need to finish ... finish”) [1].

In oral spontaneous speech, there is such a thing as "interrupting". This is an indicator of the polythematic nature of spontaneous speech. “Interrupting” is manifested in interrupting oneself, when the speaker quickly moves from one topic to another, thereby breaking off the started phrase [3, p. 65].

Sportscasters use a variety of language to describe competitions. Among the linguistic means, a special place is occupied by means of artistic expression - tropes and stylistic figures. Note that the most frequently used tropes are metaphor, epithet, metonymy, comparison, hyperbole, litote, etc. [5]. Among the figures used by sports commentators, the main ones are: rhetorical question, rhetorical exclamation, rhetorical appeal, antithesis and inversion [5].

Based on the fact that commenting on the event is carried out live, the linguistic specificity of the speech of commentators lies, first of all, in the use of emotional and evaluative vocabulary. A sports commentator, in a fit of joy for his favorite team, or, on the contrary, overcome by despair from a loss, is unable to restrain his overwhelming feelings, which he actively shares with the audience. The practical material for the study was videos in English, taken from YouTube, representing competitions in such sports as football, hockey, basketball, boxing and snooker.

A striking characteristic of the speech of sports commentators is expression - "expressive and pictorial qualities of speech that distinguish it from ordinary (or stylistically neutral) and give it figurativeness and emotional coloring" [1, p. 524]. One of the reasons for using expression in sports commentary is the fact that the commentator - a virtual interlocutor - solves a pragmatic task with its help: establishing a dialogue with the viewer.

In our opinion, one of the most emotional football commentators is the Englishman Martin Tyler. In 2003, he was named the best commentator of the decade. One of the clearest examples is his reaction to Didier Drogba's Champions League final goal against Bayern Munich: "Drogbaaa!!! And he pulled the rabbit out of the hat again! Can you believe it? Chelsea just won't let go of the Champions League" [3] Martin Tyler uses a large number of exclamatory constructions, rhetorical questions, involving the viewer in a dialogue. Admiring the skill of the athlete, he uses the phrase “to pull the rabbit out of the hat” (get the rabbit out of the hat), comparing Drogba with a magician.

Another football commentator Alan Smith is also famous for his expression. This can be illustrated by the reaction to Wayne Rooney's goal against Manchester City: "Rooney!!! It defies description. How about sensational? How about superb?" [4].

At American football competitions, commentators are also characterized by expressive reactions. So, in the last quarter of the school league match, the home team of Plano East scores a touchdown and takes the lead. The reaction of the commentator was: “Throw... What a one, god almighty, they win, I don't believe it. They're making the greatest comeback of all time!” [5].

But in the same match, literally in the next attack (it was the last one), the guests' players took advantage of the unfortunate mistake of the hosts' defense. Apparently, the host side relaxed too early and missed the victory. Perhaps the most important thing in their lives. The commentator was desperate: “Oh no, oh no, no, oh my god, no, come on, no, God bless all...I'm

sick, I'm on a throw up... [5]. Thus, the commentator conveys his disappointment from the loss, which is all the more offensive the closer the victory was.

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Swear words can be used to criticize players, such as "Man that sucked!" [6] This was said by a commentator during an NFL game because he condemned the hitter for his mistake. However, obscene words can also be used to express an overflowing commentator's delight: "Oh sh * t, that's a brilliant save!" [7] is the expression of English commentator Jonathan Pearce during a football match between Chelsea and West Bromwich in 2013, where he praised the goalkeeper for not letting the ball go into the goal.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn: expression is an integral characteristic of the speech of sports commentators, which is explained both by the unpredictable and gambling nature of the sport itself and by their work on the air. The use of emotional-evaluative vocabulary and expressive syntactic constructions forms a speech personality and a memorable style of commenting. Evaluative nouns, unusual epithets, action verbs, interjections, rhetorical questions and exclamations, hyperbole, metaphors, phraseological units, even obscene vocabulary - all this serves as a means to "infect" the viewer with the commentator's emotions, to involve him in a sports action and satisfy the need for empathy with the game .

Thus, we can note that during a sporting event, the commentator puts into his report an expressive author's vision of the game, experience, emotions, assessments, and language skills.

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